

WHAT ARE THE DIFFERENT OPTIONS TO ELIMINATE VARICOSE VEINS?

The varicose vein has no actual goal in the vascular system. For this reason, if the individual wishes to have it extracted, there is no genuine threat to the body function. There are a number of methods that may be counted when thinking to remove varicose veins. These are both surgical and non-surgical procedures. The non-surgical **vein treatments** have proven to have fewer side effects and be more successful.

There are two very popular [vein treatments California](#) to assassinate a varicose vein non-surgically. The first of these **vein treatments in San Diego** is Sclerotherapy.

Sclerotherapy:

This method is best when the vein to be removed is smaller to medium-sized. It entails an injection of medication into the actual vein. The more effective medications include polidocanol, sodium tetradecyl sulphate, and sclerosis. Medical professionals use hypertonic saline, glycerine, and Chromated glycerin in this procedure to offer more effective results.

Once these medications have been delivered into the vein through an injection, they cause the vein to die and go away. In this **vein treatment in San Jose**, the problematic vein is permanently extracted. One should be wary with this and other procedures, that they may solve the problem with one particular vein, but varicosity may then occur in a different vein.

Endovenous Treatment:

The second non-surgical **vein treatment la Jolla** is called Endovenous Treatment. This is a laser vein treatment. Typically used in combination with an ultrasound to outline the specific area of the vein to be killed. This method is the precise option when having a larger vein withdrawn.

Endovenous **varicose vein treatment la Jolla** entails a catheter being embedded into the offending vein. This is performed in order to seal off the vein in question and render it moot to the vascular system. This is one of the more desired methods to use because it has a minimum chance of scarring.

Many of the non-surgical **varicose vein treatments near me in California** can be performed in about 45 minutes, in an outpatient setting. One needs to remember with surgical and non-surgical methods that once the vein is removed, it will never grow back again.

Stripping and Ligation:

Other outpatient procedures include stripping and ligation. One can have them done in a hospital by a [vein specialist near me](#), but this will cost substantially more than being performed in an outpatient setting.

These two procedures use general anaesthesia. The **vein doctor** starts this mode of treatment by making small incisions in the skin. The procedure of stripping causes varicose vein removal, and ligation involves the tying off of the vein and the elimination of the vein matter below the tie off-site.

Ambulatory Phlebectomy:

There is also the choice of Ambulatory Phlebectomy. This procedure uses local anesthesia. The swollen vein is then removed through a series of small cuts made in the skin above the offending vein. Their elimination is done using a surgical hook.

Most vein treatment methodology is insignificantly obtrusive and utilizes local anesthesia. After the vein elimination procedure, your blood starts circulating through the healthy veins to manage the requirement for the harmed vein. Soon after your methodology, you can assume that pain and swelling should go away eventually as your body heals.